

A Generalized Method for proving the Theorem derived from the Binomial Coefficients in Combinatorial Geometric Series

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Abstract: This paper presents binomial and factorial theorems on the binomial coefficients in combinatorial geometric series. The coefficient for each term in combinatorial geometric series refers to a binomial coefficient. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to develop the multiple summations of geometric series, a new idea was stimulated his mind to create a combinatorial geometric series [1-13]. The combinatorial geometric series is a geometric series whose coefficient of each term of the geometric series denotes the binomial coefficient V_n^r . In this article, binomial identities and multinomial theorem is provided using the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [1-13] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient V_n^r .

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \dots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \dots (n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series.

Theorem 2.1: $V_n^r = \frac{(n+r)!}{n! r!}$ where $n, r \geq 0$ & $n, r \in N$.

Proof. $\binom{n+r}{n} = \frac{(n+r)!}{n!(n+r-n)!} = \frac{(n+r)!}{n! r!} = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \dots (n+r)}{r!}$.

Here, $V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3) \dots (n+r)}{r!} = \prod_{i=1}^r \frac{n+i}{r!}$.

From the above expressions, we conclude that

$$V_n^r = \frac{(n+r)!}{n!r!}, \text{ where } n, r \geq 0 \text{ \& } n, r \in N.$$

Theorem 2. 1: $pV_{qn}^{pn} = (p+q)V_{qn}^{pn-1}, (n, p, q \geq 1 \text{ \& } n, p, q \in N).$

Proof. Let us prove this theorem using Theorem 2.1.

$$\begin{aligned} : pV_{qn}^{pn} &= (p+q)V_{qn}^{pn-1} \Rightarrow p \frac{(pn+qn)!}{(pn)!(qn)!} = (p+q) \frac{(qn+pn-1)!}{(qn)!(pn-1)!} \\ \Rightarrow p \frac{(pn+qn)!}{(pn)!} &= (p+q) \frac{(qn+pn-1)!}{(pn-1)!} \Rightarrow p \frac{(qn+pn-1)!(pn+qn)}{(pn-1)!(pn)} \\ &= (p+q) \frac{(qn+pn-1)!}{(pn-1)!} \Rightarrow p \frac{(pn+qn)}{pn} = (p+q). \end{aligned}$$

By simplifying this expression, we get that $(p+q) = (p+q)$.

Hence, theorem is proved.

Note that the proof for Theorem 2.2 refers to a generalized method.

Corollary 2. 1: $qV_{pn}^{qn} = (p+q)V_{pn}^{qn-1}, (n, p, q \geq 1 \text{ \& } n, p, q \in N).$

Conclusion

In this article, binomial and factorial theorems [1-13] were built using the binomial theorem on the binomial coefficients in combinatorial geometric series. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers for research and development further.

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